

1 **HIV-2 infection in humans.**

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6 We measured total transcription by microarray in the whole blood in humans with HIV-2 infection and
7 compared it to infection in humans with HIV-1 infection. Humans with HIV-2 infection displayed activation
8 of *Card19* in the whole blood and produced excess *IL37*. Exhaustion dynamics during lentiviral infection in
9 vivo were different in humans with HIV-2, with silencing of *Eomes*.

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